

D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan

for
HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01
Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Action Acronym:
FASS

Action Full Title:
"Fast and Accurate Solubility for Sustainability"

Grant Agreement No.: 101159068

Document Properties

Deliverable	D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan
Lead beneficiary	EU-OS
Contributing beneficiary	all partners
Author(s)	Robert Harmel, Nathan Dupertuis, Martin Kuentz, Nicolas Francisco, Judith Graf
Type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Delivery date	30.11.2024

Table of Contents

Executive summary	3
Background	3
Main communication and dissemination goals	3
Target audiences and messages	4
Communication and dissemination tools	5
Website	5
Social media	6
Publications	6
Events	6
Instrument demonstrations	6
Newsletter	7
Mass media	7
Style and branding material	7
Key performance indicators	7
Conclusions	8

Executive summary

The FASS Dissemination and Communication plan ensures to raise awareness and highlight the achievements of the project to respective interest groups and facilitates the use of the results to maximize long-term impact. It displays the key messages delivered to the different audiences and the strategies to reach these audiences including all the tools and channels needed. The key audiences span from potential customers, over decision makers until investors to create a sustainable business model, gain acceptance of the technology, support science and the European society, and to create opportunities for further expansion of the technology's scope beyond the project lifetime.

Background

Measuring small molecule solubility is a necessary but labour-intensive process that often requires substantial amounts of chemicals. Current methods are either fast but inaccurate or slow but precise, both necessitating excessive chemical use. The aim of the FASS project is to advance the state of the art in solubility measurements by introducing a new sustainable solution based on high-efficiency second harmonic scattering that saves up to 90% of cost, 90% of measurement time, 99% of chemicals and 97% of electricity and 80% of compounds compared to the gold standard.

The FASS consortium consists of the startup Oryl Photonics bringing the instrument to market and developing a business model; ALPhANOV, a research and technology organization to support technology maturation. EU-OPENSOURCE ERIC; a European Research Consortium to enable customer development and instrument demonstration; and FHWN, a centre for pharmaceutical research to explore value-added applications of FASS in drug discovery and development.

Main communication and dissemination goals

The FASS projects drives a disruptive technology towards its market entry and consequently, the main communication and dissemination goals are:

- raising awareness and understanding of the technology and its potential among researchers from industry and public institutions
- promote project results, developments and upcoming opportunities to key stakeholders
- increasing the visibility of the project goals to attract potential customers during and beyond the project lifetime.

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101159068 and from the Swiss Confederation Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.

Target audiences and messages

To maximize its impact, the FASS project needs to reach a variety of stakeholders and audiences. The key communication messages transferred to each group are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Audiences and corresponding key messages.

Audience	Key message
Academic and industry researchers (customers)	<p>FASS will deliver a new instrument that can produce accurate results within in a short time for many samples saving time, money and other resources.</p> <p>FASS will provide FAIR* solubility data for small molecules tested.</p> <p>FASS can collaborate with other research projects that are in line with the FASS project goals.</p> <p>FASS will explore novel fields of applications beyond solubility measurements.</p>
Professionals from SMEs, pharmaceutical and chemical companies (customers)	<p>FASS will provide a solubility service to measure a large number of small molecule samples, in a rapid and accurate way, at a reasonable price.</p> <p>FASS will provide instrument demonstrations on the new TRL6 prototype to showcase the benefits of the technology.</p> <p>FASS will deliver a new comprehensive analysis of the value proposition.</p>
Decision/policy makers	<p>FASS technology offers a highly sustainable and accurate technology which is ideal to make research and industry greener.</p>
Investors	<p>FASS will commercialize a disruptive technology that advances the current state of the art in solubility testing with great potential to extend its capabilities into other areas.</p>
Students and early career scientists	<p>FASS will provide training and educational opportunities to this group to make them aware of the disruptive technology.</p>
General public	<p>FASS will exploit the project results to support the Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe (2020 report) while raising the competitiveness and resource efficiency of the European economy and contributing to the health sector.</p>

*FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101159068 and from the Swiss Confederation Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.

Communication and dissemination tools

To reach our target groups, we will use a variety of tools which are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Systematic overview of the communication types.

Type	Channel	Primary audience(s)	Intended reach	Intended frequency	Management	Resourcing
Website	News	A&IR, CP, DM, Inv, PS, S&ECS, GP	international	monthly	EU-OS	low
	Events	A&IR, CP, Inv, PS, S&ECS	international		Oryl	low
	General information	GP	international		EU-OS	low
Social media	LinkedIn	A&IR, CP, PS, S&ECS, Inv	international	Bi-weekly	EU-OS, Oryl	low
Publications	Scientific journals	A&IR, CP, PS, S&ECS	international	when possible	all partners	high
	Zenodo	A&IR, CP, PS, S&ECS	international	when needed	EU-OS	low
Events	Partner events and external conferences	A&IR, CP, DM, Inv, PS, S&ECS, GP	international	when possible	Oryl	high
Instrument demonstration	in-person demonstration	A&IR, CP, DM, Inv, PS, S&ECS, GP	individuals	when possible	Oryl	high
Newsletter	Email	A&IR, CP, PS, S&ECS	international	3-6 monthly	EU-OS	low
Mass media	Press release, interviews	GP	international	when needed	Oryl, EU-OS	moderate

*Academic and industry researchers (A&IR), Company professionals (CP), Decision/policy makers (DM), Investors (Inv), Preclinical scientist (PS), Students and early career scientists (S&ECS); General public (GP)

Website

The most critical communication channel will be the FASS website hosted under <https://fass-solubility.eu/>. It will serve as central point to provide all relevant project information including news, facts around the technology and the consortium goals, and a contact form to collaborate with us, request an instrument demo or a solubility service. It will be referenced in newsletters, social media or via other relevant channels. The news section will cover important milestones within the project, announcing conference participation in advance, mirrors interviews and communication in other media for general public. More information on the specific structure of the website can be found in deliverable "D6.1 Project Logo and Website".

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101159068 and from the Swiss Confederation Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.

Social media

The FASS project will be supported by a combination of LinkedIn accounts from the project partners (EU-OPENSREEN, ALPhANOV, Oryl Photonics, FHNW) and a dedicated FASS project page. The FASS LinkedIn page will be used to prepare news flashes and announcements which will be shared by all four partners via their channels to maximize the reach of the project and engage more potential customers and stakeholders. We will introduce the project partners and objectives, provide insight into the technology and share important milestones of the project. Importantly, we will utilize this channel to highlight our participation in events that we attend or organize to maximize participation and interaction with potential customers or collaborators.

Publications

Publishing articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals is an important mean to transfer the current value proposition of the instrument convincingly and to create a perspective on potential future applications. We will promote technology/science-related publications from partner and capitalize on them to promote the FASS project itself. In parallel, we are planning to have a publication providing a comparison between the developed instrumentation and available market-competitive technologies and a paper highlighting new applications potentially in the pharmaceutical area.

Events

Partner events and external conferences are critical platforms to increase awareness of the project and to highlight important project achievements to a broad range of stakeholders. The consortium partners are planning to attend conferences in pharmaceutical and life science sectors that target industry and academia such as SLAS, CPHI, ELRIG, the European Chemical Biology Symposium (ECBS), the world meeting of pharmaceuticals and biopharmaceuticals and the European Conference on Pharmaceuticals. In addition, we will join investor events to increase our network among business angels, venture capital firms, corporate venture capital firms and family offices, and pave the road for future fundraising needed to finance the next steps of the project. For the general public, consortium partner will make us open door days as e.g. the "Long Night of Sciences Berlin".

Instrument demonstrations

During the project lifetime, we will offer instrument demonstrations based on identified demand at USC in Santiago de Compostela, at EU-OPENSREEN in Berlin, at ALPhANOV in Bordeaux, at Oryl Photonics in Lausanne or at FHNW in Basel. During such demonstrations, people will learn more about the technology, the instrument handling and its scope. This will be highly useful to convince and train customer in a small face-to-face event.

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101159068 and from the Swiss Confederation Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.

Newsletter

EU-OPENSOURCE and ALPhANOV will harness their newsletters to reach a broader audience in their field. For example, EU-POPENSOURCE newsletter reaches more than 1500 individuals with interest in drug discovery and chemical biology. The newsletter is sent out every 3 months and will be used to raise awareness of the project, communicate project results and guide a broad audience to the FASS website.

Mass media

During the project, we will engage in presentations, interviews and communication through general media (newspaper, websites, radio, podcasts etc), to reach and educate the general public, and announce significant milestones.

Style and branding material

A logo and a common design concept for the project has been provided and described in deliverable "D6.1 Project Logo and Website". Templates for communication activities are available via the "Dissemination and Communication" section on the internal FASS SharePoint.

Key performance indicators

Efficient communication and dissemination of the project and its results is the key to spark interest in the technology and attract early adopters and customers. The following key performance indicators (KPIs) are collected to monitor the outreach activities:

- Number of new posts on the website
- Number of website visitors (google analytics)
- Number of newsletter posts
- Number of social media posts
- Number of social media post views and average engagement rate on posts
- Number of publications
- Number of publication views, downloads and citations
- Number of mass media press releases and interviews
- Number of instrument demonstrations
- Number of instrument demonstration participants
- Number of conferences visits
- Number of user/customers that request the solubility service or an instrument demonstration with respect to the different channels

Conclusions

All in all, we designed a clear communication plan that engages all relevant stakeholders for the FASS project. It will raise awareness among potential customers and other interest groups which helps to convince them of the full potential of this our new disruptive instrumentation. EU-OPENSREEN together with Oryl Photonics will lead and coordinate the outreach and dissemination activities with support from ALPhANOV and FHNW. KPI will be implemented to monitor and improve the quality of our outreach activities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101159068 and from the Swiss Confederation Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.

